

Developing a growth mindset in education: a bibliometric analysis and its challenge during pandemic

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ABSTRACT

The growth mindset is essential for learning because students encounter numerous obstacles during the pandemic. However, only a few studies have examined research trends in growth mindset pedagogy. In filling this gap, this study aims to conduct a bibliometric study using the growth mindset pedagogy during the pandemic. Data from 81 Scopus-sourced scholarly articles on growth mindset in education from 2020–2022 was used. VOSviewer qualitatively analyzed the data. Results showed that the research cluster's growth mindset is diverse and adaptive to learning dynamics, notably during the COVID-19 pandemic. Several research clusters examined instructors, students, and parents' roles in learning. Another cluster focuses on academic achievement and teacher efforts to improve student performance. The research addresses student issues like depression, academic fatigue, and suicide ideation. Research on a growth mindset in education has grown quantitatively since 2021. Clusters 1, 2, and 4, 5 have the most research on active learning design to improve student academic performance and accomplishment through teachers and other supporting elements. Even though academic fatigue can lead to depression and suicidal ideation, research on academic achievement-related student issues is scarce. In conclusion, a growth mindset can significantly enhance academic performance and solve learning problems.

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1. INTRODUCTION

The global education system faces new challenges due to the spread of the COVID-19 virus. Teachers and students must adjust to new regulations and practices. Students had several challenges throughout the pandemic, causing stress [1], increased anxiety and distress [2], loss of interest in educational activities, decreased student involvement in the educational process [3], diminished quality of student interaction with peers [4], and reduced motivation [5], [6]. Many students also complained of difficulties concentrating during online learning, and busy assignments [7], [8].

Students can either grow from their obstacles or give in to them. Identifying and solving those obstacles requires a mindset [9], [10]. Mindset varies from fixed to growth mindsets [9]. A growth mindset is a belief that one's qualities can change with others' efforts, strategies, or assistance. However, fixed mindset

individuals accept that the self-quality is given because they view their intelligence as unchanging and unmodifiable, so any work they do is predetermined [9], [11]. Thus, a growth mindset should benefit pupils experiencing challenges [12]. Previous research found the significance of the growth mindset in fostering college students' learning engagement [13] and academic success during COVID-19 [14], [15].

Growth mindset persons are more likely to persevere and progress when faced with challenges. Fixed-mindset people avoid challenges, fail to maximize their potential [16], and give up easily [9]. With a fixed mindset, people often feel helpless and blame their academic failure. However, students with a growth mindset view failure as challenging to learn, improve their quality, and achieve higher [9].

The topic of growth mindset pedagogy has received much attention from previous researchers. Therefore, research trend mapping is carried out to determine the research dynamics on this topic. In general, researchers use various methods: a systematic literature review [11], [17], scoping literature review [18], a meta-analysis [19], and bibliometrics [20]. These studies examine the growth mindset based on its relationship with mathematics education [20], psychological distress [19], and human resource development [18].

The previous study was applied to the elementary school level [11], [17]. The study results show that the growth mindset can increase student achievement and involvement in learning [11], [20] and enhance mental health [19]. Thus, growth mindset pedagogy improves academic performance and mental stability. Despite limited research, the growth mindset improves learning and academic achievement. The growth mindset pedagogy study was small-scale and integrated with particular interventions [17]. Finding a central study theme to uncover systematic development patterns becomes difficult as the area evolves. Research trends reveal topic overviews, knowledge gaps, novel ideas, and future research prospects [21], [22].

Furthermore, based on a new viewpoint on the importance of particular articles, authors, concepts, and writings related to these essential studies [23], [24], bibliometric research may offer academics the necessary framework for establishing the significance of their contributions to the topic [21]. Thus, scientific progress from global to author levels could be assessed by the bibliometric analysis [25] to understand the issue better and recognize teaching and learning research variables. Based on this background, this study fills the gap by examining three research focuses on growth mindset pedagogy: i) the research cluster; ii) the topic changes annually; iii) the research direction based on research density. This study maps growth mindset research patterns in education during a pandemic to identify more research opportunities.

2. RESEARCH METHOD

2.1. Research design

The research method is bibliometric analysis, conducted in quantitative [23], [26], and qualitative research [21]. Bibliometric analysis is a popular and rigorous method of obtaining, researching, and interpreting quantifiable data using published research articles' mathematical and statistical analysis to assess publication information and untied the evolutionary complexities of the subject field [21], [27]. Bibliometric quantifies, evaluates publications, and assesses qualitative research impact using peer review [21], [27].

2.2. Selection criteria for the articles

Scopus bibliographical data was retrieved via article search. Based on relevant theory, this study searched for 'growth mindset in education' and 'growth mindset in learning' during 2019–2022. The search terms used to retrieve relevant sources from the Scopus database are detailed in Table 1.

Table 1. Search string

Search strings
<p><i>TITLE-ABS</i> <i>KEY (growth AND mindset AND in AND education) AND (LIMIT-TO (PUBYEAR , 2022) OR LIMIT-TO (PUBYEAR , 2021) OR LIMIT-TO (PUBYEAR , 2020) OR LIMIT-TO (PUBYEAR , 2019) AND (LIMIT-TO (DOCTYPE , "ar") OR LIMIT-TO (DOCTYPE , "cp") OR LIMIT-TO (DOCTYPE , "re")) AND (LIMIT-TO (SUBJAREA , "SOC1") OR LIMIT-TO (SUBJAREA , "ARTS")) AND (LIMIT-TO (EXACTKEYWORD , "Growth mindset in education") OR LIMIT-TO (EXACTKEYWORD , "Growth mindset in learning")) AND (LIMIT-TO (LANGUAGE , "English")) AND (LIMIT-TO (SRCTYPE , "j") OR LIMIT-TO (SRCTYPE , "p"))</i></p>

Figure 1 shows the search query-driven methods for selecting articles. We retrieved 935 growth mindsets in education and learning articles from the Scopus database. After filtering, 81 papers were left for review. Those papers fulfil the study's requirements.

strategies and classroom management depending on learning difficulties and demands, notably during the COVID-19 epidemic. Cluster 3 (dark blue) features papers on how teachers can help students succeed through meaningful and pleasant learning. Cluster 3 studies how teachers assist students in overcoming learning issues that lead to depression and suicide. Secondary school, notably in Korea, is this cluster's concentration.

Cluster 4 (yellow) examines how difficulty, persistence, commitment to goals, and parental support affect learning performance. On the other hand, research trends also investigate the negative aspects of achievement orientation, which can cause depressive symptoms. Cluster 5 (purple) highlights self-efficacy, participation, and learning requirements, especially at the university level, as characteristics that affect student competency. Cluster 6 (bright blue) studies educator-created learning settings in start-up-based learning frameworks, especially in engineering. Cluster 7 (orange) discusses education issues such as authoritarian parenting and fraud, notably in China. Cluster 8 (brown) addresses two learning attainment demands that affect student academic achievement and fatigue. Cluster 9 (pink) discusses student motivation and rewards.

The growth mindset in education research examines the roles of teachers, students, and parents. For student achievement, teachers promote active, pleasant, and meaningful learning. Academic success requires enthusiasm, commitment, and persistence. Thus, motivating students for their learning attempts is crucial. Nonetheless, focusing on academic achievement can lead to depression, academic burnout, and even suicide among students. Authoritarian parenting also causes learning issues. Therefore, it can be concluded that a growth mindset can substantially contribute to improving learning outcomes and resolving learning problems. It is crucial to present the research impact based on the most cited articles.

Table 2 illustrates that growth mindset research focuses on psychological factors, gender disparities, and classroom practices. This study found a link between growth mindset teaching, student psychological characteristics, and gender disparities. In addition, some research focuses on academic achievement and STEM.

Table 2. Most cited papers in a growth mindset in education

No	Title	Cluster	Source	TC	C/Y
1	Building grit: The longitudinal pathways between mindset, commitment, grit, and academic outcomes	4	[30]	75	25
2	In search of a growth mindset pedagogy: A case study of one teacher's classroom practices in a Finnish elementary school	1	[31]	38	12.6
3	Growing a growth mindset: characterizing how and why undergraduate students' mindsets change	5	[32]	27	13.5
4	The conundrum of low achievement and feedback for learning	5	[33]	24	12.0
5	CS1: how will they do? How can we help? A decade of research and practice	1	[34]	23	7.6
6	Can test anxiety interventions alleviate a gender gap in an undergraduate STEM course?	1	[35]	21	7.0
7	Growing STEM: Perceived faculty mindset as an indicator of communal affordances in STEM	1	[36]	16	5.3
8	Enhancing children's math motivation with a joint intervention on mindset and gender stereotypes	1	[37]	10	10.0
9	Growth mindset and its predictive validity—do migration background and academic validation matter?	5	[38]	9	3.0
10	Inclusion of students with learning, emotional, and behavioral disabilities through strength-based approaches	3	[39]	9	3.0
11	Promoting a growth mindset in CS1: Does one size fit all? A pilot study	1	[40]	9	4.5
12	What are the potential predictors of psychological capital for Chinese primary school teachers?	7	[41]	8	2.6
13	Testing the association of growth mindset and grades across a challenging transition: Is growth mindset associated with grades?	4	[42]	8	4.0
14	Measuring mastery behaviors at scale: The persistence, effort, resilience, and challenge-seeking (PERC) task	5	[43]	8	4.0
15	Which boys and which girls are falling behind? Linking adolescents' gender role profiles to motivation, engagement, and achievement	9	[44]	8	8.0

3.2. Research overlay on growth mindset in education

Based on the finding of this study, the quantity and interest of study topics in growth mindset studies fluctuate throughout time. This study also found that growth mindset research in education has increased quantitatively since 2021. Figure 3 shows research overlay results. Figure 3 shows that from 2019 to mid-2020, research trends centered on learning success, academic achievement, student outcomes, STEM, and gender differences. Until early 2021, trends include vibrant, fun, and meaningful learning designs with motivation and the involvement of teacher and parents in achieving student academic success. In mid-2021, researchers study academic fatigue, depression, and suicidal thoughts. Classroom management, work engagement, conceptual comprehension, effort praise, transformational leadership, depression, and authoritative parenting style become research subjects 2022.

Figure 3. Research overlay on growth mindset in education

3.3. Research density on growth mindset in education

The proliferation of research indicates an annual trend towards growth mindset in the field of education. The number of studies also serves as an indicator of the level of attention that researchers devote to the topic. Quantitative publication data is presented in Table 3. The table reveals that growth mindset education research did not improve significantly between 2019 and 2020. However, publishing numbers will rise significantly in 2021 and maybe through 2022. The number of publications determines research density.

Table 3. Number of annual publications in a growth mindset in education

Period	Total publication
2019	14
2020	16
2021	30
2022	21
Total	81

Figure 4 shows that the most frequently researched topic related to a growth mindset is the role of teachers and growth mindset practices in learning. A growth mindset is also often researched as a factor influencing students’ development and achievement. From a multidisciplinary perspective, a growth mindset is often associated with psychological constructs, such as grit, engagement, flow, and motivation.

Figure 4. Item density on growth mindset in education

applies the growth mindset in small groups or individually. However, the growth mindset is still not widely used in school curriculums.

The present curriculum requires teachers to have pedagogical competency [57]. Teachers must understand and implement curriculum changes. In this way, teachers can facilitate learning that promotes student competence [58]. Previous research found that teacher interventions were less significant than student interventions [10] because of substantial and technical obstacles, which teachers can overcome by continuing to investigate knowledge and gaining experience through practice [57].

A growth mindset study has also explored its effects on education. Internal variables from the individual and external environmental factors influence the growth mindset. Self-efficacy in particular topics [49] and motivation have been researched as individual growth mindset elements. On the other side, extrinsic factors include teacher beliefs, parent mindsets, classroom instruction, socioeconomic status, school environment [11], [59]–[62], and parenting style [63]. Those internal and external factors optimize a growth mindset in learning. Students can develop motivation and self-efficacy if teachers, parents, and the school environment are supportive. The earlier study also emphasizes parental involvement in students' activities and parenting styles [64].

The growth mindset's antecedents, mainly internal processes, are less studied than its effects. Future studies can examine internal processes affecting student growth mindsets and create specific programs. Additionally, growth mindset research still emphasizes academic achievement because teachers manage subjects to help students succeed [51]. However, academic achievement-related student difficulties are rarely studied. Moreover, little research has been conducted on how the growth mindset affects noncognitive aspects like welfare, resilience, student self-esteem and cognitive factors like problem-solving and decision-making. It is an essential topic because academic fatigue, which can lead to depression and suicidal ideation, is common among college students.

Grit, growth mindset, and other constructs are frequently investigated [15], [45], [46]. Growth mindset people are more hopeful and persistent because they have self-transcendent motivation for learning [47], [48]. A growth mindset was also linked to grit [15]. Thus, grit changes growth mindset and vice versa. Most research has examined the reciprocal relationship between a growth mindset and grit in usually developing learners. However, inclusion and special education research are few. Grit and growth mindset research is intriguing since special needs kids have unique dynamics.

5. CONCLUSION

According to the findings, growth mindset research is extensive. Active learning design has been thoroughly investigated to improve student academic performance through the teacher's role, growth mindset, and grit. Additionally, many growth mindset issues can be explored. Some involve including the growth mindset in the curriculum, internal variables that drive it, and inclusive education. This research suggests that learning and student internal processes must be emphasized, particularly the growth mindset. An excellent education should boost student well-being and self-actualization. An alliance encompassing the government, educators, parents, students, and students is necessary to advance health, well-being, and education in alignment with the sustainable development goals (SDGs). Moreover, the governor should develop a mental health and well-being curriculum. The curriculum can be taught alone or alongside related courses. The mental health and well-being curriculum teaches resilience, growth mindset, coping, and soft skills.

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REFERENCES

- [1] B. N. Parahita, D. Astutik, G. Ghufonudin, and Y. Yuhastina, "Learning loss experience and control motive by Zillennial generation in Indonesia," *International Journal of Evaluation and Research in Education (IJERE)*, vol. 12, no. 1, pp. 346–356, 2023, doi: 10.11591/ijere.v12i1.23824.
- [2] W. Cao *et al.*, "The psychological impact of the COVID-19 epidemic on college students in China," *Psychiatry Research*, vol. 287, no. 1, pp. 1–5, 2020, doi: 10.1016/j.psychres.2020.112934.
- [3] E. V. Frolova, T. M. Ryabova, and O. V. Rogach, "Digital technologies in education: Problems and prospects for 'Moscow electronic school' project implementation," *European Journal of Contemporary Education*, vol. 8, no. 4, pp. 779–789, 2019, doi: 10.13187/ejced.2019.4.779.
- [4] I. G. Vania, W. Yudiana, and H. Susanto, "Does online-formed peer relationship affect academic motivation during online learning?" *Journal of Educational, Health and Community Psychology*, vol. 11, no. 1, 2022, doi: 10.12928/jehcp.v11i1.21970.
- [5] C. J. Fong, "Academic motivation in a pandemic context: a conceptual review of prominent theories and an integrative model," *Educational Psychology*, vol. 42, no. 10, pp. 1204–1222, 2022, doi: 10.1080/01443410.2022.2026891.

- [6] N. Aznam, R. Perdana, J. Jumadi, H. Nurcahyo, and Y. Wiyatmo, "Motivation and satisfaction in online learning during COVID-19 pandemic: A systematic review," *International Journal of Evaluation and Research in Education (IJERE)*, vol. 11, no. 2, pp. 753–762, 2022, doi: 10.11591/ijere.v11i2.21961.
- [7] R. Nastiti and N. Hayati, "Online learning in higher education: challenges for students and lecturers amidst the pandemic (in Indonesian)," *INOBIS: Jurnal Inovasi Bisnis dan Manajemen Indonesia*, vol. 3, no. 3, pp. 378–390, 2020, doi: 10.31842/jurnalnobis.v3i3.145.
- [8] A. Patricia Aguilera-Hermida, "College students' use and acceptance of emergency online learning due to COVID-19," *International Journal of Educational Research Open*, vol. 1, p. 100011, 2020, doi: 10.1016/j.ijedro.2020.100011.
- [9] M. A. Sahagun, R. Moser, J. Shomaker, and J. Fortier, "Developing a growth-mindset pedagogy for higher education and testing its efficacy," *Social Sciences and Humanities Open*, vol. 4, no. 1, pp. 1–8, 2021, doi: 10.1016/j.ssaho.2021.100168.
- [10] D. S. Yeager and C. S. Dweck, "What can be learned from growth mindset controversies?" *American Psychologist*, vol. 75, no. 9, pp. 1269–1284, 2020, doi: 10.1037/amp0000794.
- [11] M. Spenner, "Growth mindset: trend or real science?" *Journal of Initial Teacher Inquiry*, vol. 3, no. 1, p. 53, 2017, doi: 10.26021/815.
- [12] J. L. Burnette, E. H. O'Boyle, E. M. VanEpps, J. M. Pollack, and E. J. Finkel, "Mind-sets matter: A meta-analytic review of implicit theories and self-regulation," *Psychological Bulletin*, vol. 139, no. 3, pp. 655–701, 2013, doi: 10.1037/a0029531.
- [13] H. Zhao, J. Xiong, Z. Zhang, and C. Qi, "Growth mindset and college students' learning engagement during the COVID-19 pandemic: a serial mediation model," *Frontiers in Psychology*, vol. 12, no. 1, pp. 1–10, 2021, doi: 10.3389/fpsyg.2021.621094.
- [14] M. Mosanya, "Buffering academic stress during the COVID-19 pandemic related social isolation: grit and growth mindset as protective factors against the impact of loneliness," *International Journal of Applied Positive Psychology*, vol. 6, no. 2, pp. 159–174, 2021, doi: 10.1007/s41042-020-00043-7.
- [15] D. Park, E. Tsukayama, A. Yu, and A. L. Duckworth, "The development of grit and growth mindset during adolescence," *Journal of Experimental Child Psychology*, vol. 198, no. 1, pp. 1–11, 2020, doi: 10.1016/j.jecp.2020.104889.
- [16] C. S. Dweck and D. S. Yeager, "Mindsets: a view from two eras," *Perspectives on Psychological Science*, vol. 14, no. 3, pp. 481–496, 2019, doi: 10.1177/1745691618804166.
- [17] H. Savvides and C. Bond, "How does growth mindset inform interventions in primary schools? A systematic literature review," *Educational Psychology in Practice*, vol. 37, no. 2, pp. 134–149, 2021, doi: 10.1080/02667363.2021.1879025.
- [18] S. J. Han and V. Stieha, "Growth mindset for human resource development: a scoping review of the literature with recommended interventions," *Human Resource Development Review*, vol. 19, no. 3, pp. 309–331, 2020, doi: 10.1177/1534484320939739.
- [19] J. L. Burnette, L. E. Knouse, D. T. Vavra, E. O'Boyle, and M. A. Brooks, "Growth mindsets and psychological distress: A meta-analysis," *Clinical Psychology Review*, vol. 77, no. 1, pp. 1–13, 2020, doi: 10.1016/j.cpr.2020.101816.
- [20] X. Xu, Q. Zhang, J. Sun, and Y. Wei, "A bibliometric review on latent topics and research trends in the growth mindset literature for mathematics education," *Frontiers in Psychology*, vol. 13, no. 1, pp. 1–15, 2022, doi: 10.3389/fpsyg.2022.1039761.
- [21] N. Donthu, S. Kumar, D. Mukherjee, N. Pandey, and W. M. Lim, "How to conduct a bibliometric analysis: An overview and guidelines," *Journal of Business Research*, vol. 133, no. 1, pp. 285–296, 2021, doi: 10.1016/j.jbusres.2021.04.070.
- [22] L. Plonsky, "Study quality in quantitative L2 research (1990-2010): A methodological synthesis and call for reform," *Modern Language Journal*, vol. 98, no. 1, pp. 450–470, 2014, doi: 10.1111/j.1540-4781.2014.12058.x.
- [23] L. Lei and D. Liu, "Research trends in applied linguistics from 2005 to 2016: A bibliometric analysis and its implications," *Applied Linguistics*, vol. 40, no. 3, pp. 540–561, 2019, doi: 10.1093/applin/amy003.
- [24] D. R. Radev, M. T. Joseph, B. Gibson, and P. Muthukrishnan, "A Bibliometric and network analysis of the field of computational linguistics," *Journal of the Association for Information Science and Technology*, vol. 67, no. 3, pp. 683–706, 2015.
- [25] A. Syahid and A. Qodir, "Journal of Language and Linguistic Studies: A fifteen-year bibliometric quest for a bigger impact," *Journal of Language and Linguistic Studies*, vol. 17, no. 1, pp. 290–314, 2021, doi: 10.17263/jlls.903415.
- [26] X. Zhang, "A bibliometric analysis of second language acquisition between 1997 and 2018," *Studies in Second Language Acquisition*, vol. 42, no. 1, pp. 199–222, 2020, doi: 10.1017/S0272263119000573.
- [27] A. Agarwal et al., "Bibliometrics: Tracking research impact by selecting the appropriate metrics," *Asian Journal of Andrology*, vol. 18, no. 2, pp. 296–309, 2016, doi: 10.4103/1008-682X.171582.
- [28] A. H. Al-Hoorie and J. P. Vitta, "The seven sins of L2 research: A review of 30 journals' statistical quality and their CiteScore, SJR, SNIP, JCR Impact Factors," *Language Teaching Research*, vol. 23, no. 6, p. 727, 2019, doi: 10.1177/1362168818767191.
- [29] S. Arnott, M. Masson, and S. Lapkin, "Exploring Trends in 21st Century Canadian K-12 French as Second Language Research: A Research Synthesis," *Canadian Journal of Applied Linguistics*, vol. 22, no. 1, pp. 60–83, 2019, doi: 10.7202/1060906ar.
- [30] X. Tang, M. Wang, J. Guo, and K. Salmela-Aro, "Building grit: the longitudinal pathways between mindset, commitment, grit, and academic outcomes," *Journal of Youth and Adolescence*, vol. 48, no. 5, pp. 850–863, 2019, doi: 10.1007/s10964-019-00998-0.
- [31] I. Rissanen, E. Kuusisto, M. Tuominen, and K. Tirri, "In search of a growth mindset pedagogy: A case study of one teacher's classroom practices in a Finnish elementary school," *Teaching and Teacher Education*, vol. 77, no. 1, pp. 204–213, 2019, doi: 10.1016/j.tate.2018.10.002.
- [32] L. B. Limeri et al., "Growing a growth mindset: characterizing how and why undergraduate students' mindsets change," *International Journal of STEM Education*, vol. 7, no. 1, 2020, doi: 10.1186/s40594-020-00227-2.
- [33] E. Pitt, M. Bearman, and R. Esterhazy, "The conundrum of low achievement and feedback for learning," *Assessment and Evaluation in Higher Education*, vol. 45, no. 2, pp. 239–250, 2020, doi: 10.1080/02602938.2019.1630363.
- [34] K. Quille and S. Bergin, "CS1: how will they do? How can we help? A decade of research and practice," *Computer Science Education*, vol. 29, no. 2–3, pp. 254–282, 2019, doi: 10.1080/08993408.2019.1612679.
- [35] R. B. Harris, D. Z. Grunspan, M. A. Pelch, G. Fernandes, G. Ramirez, and S. Freeman, "Can test anxiety interventions alleviate a gender gap in an undergraduate STEM course?" *CBE Life Sciences Education*, vol. 18, no. 3, 2019, doi: 10.1187/cbe.18-05-0083.
- [36] M. A. Fuesting, A. B. Diekmann, K. L. Boucher, M. C. Murphy, D. L. Manson, and B. L. Safer, "Growing STEM: Perceived faculty mindset as an indicator of communal affordances in STEM," *Journal of Personality and Social Psychology*, vol. 117, no. 2, pp. 260–281, 2019, doi: 10.1037/pspa0000154.
- [37] J. Lee, H. J. Lee, J. Song, and M. Bong, "Enhancing children's math motivation with a joint intervention on mindset and gender stereotypes," *Learning and Instruction*, vol. 73, 2021, doi: 10.1016/j.learninstruc.2020.101416.
- [38] D. Corradi, J. Nicolai, and F. Levrau, "Growth mindset and its predictive validity—do migration background and academic validation matter?" *Higher Education*, vol. 77, no. 3, pp. 491–504, 2019, doi: 10.1007/s10734-018-0286-6.
- [39] J. D. Garwood and A. A. Ampuja, "Inclusion of students with learning, emotional, and behavioral disabilities through strength-based approaches," *Intervention in School and Clinic*, vol. 55, no. 1, pp. 46–51, 2019, doi: 10.1177/1053451218767918.
- [40] K. Quille and S. Bergin, "Promoting a growth mindset in CS1: does one size fit all? a pilot study," in *Annual Conference on Innovation and Technology in Computer Science Education, ITiCSE*, 2020, pp. 12–18. doi: 10.1145/3341525.3387361.

- [41] X. Chen, G. Zeng, E. C. Chang, and H. Y. Cheung, "What are the potential predictors of psychological capital for Chinese primary school teachers?" *Frontiers in Education*, vol. 4, no. 1, pp. 1–8, 2019, doi: 10.3389/educ.2019.00050.
- [42] Y. Li and T. C. Bates, "Testing the association of growth mindset and grades across a challenging transition: Is growth mindset associated with grades?" *Intelligence*, vol. 81, no. 1, pp. 1–8, 2020, doi: 10.1016/j.intell.2020.101471.
- [43] T. Porter *et al.*, "Measuring mastery behaviours at scale: The persistence, effort, resilience, and challenges-seeking (PERC) task," *Journal of Learning Analytics*, vol. 7, no. 1, pp. 5–18, 2020, doi: 10.18608/jla.2020.71.2.
- [44] J. Yu, R. McLellan, and L. Winter, "Which boys and which girls are falling behind? linking adolescents' gender role profiles to motivation, engagement, and achievement," *Journal of Youth and Adolescence*, vol. 50, no. 2, pp. 336–352, 2021, doi: 10.1007/s10964-020-01293-z.
- [45] J. L. Larberg and L. H. Sherlin, "Grit and growth mindset contribution to school counseling services," *SAGE Open*, vol. 11, no. 2, pp. 1–10, 2021, doi: 10.1177/21582440211014512.
- [46] D. Sethi and S. Shashwati, "Say no to setbacks: Grit & growth mindset have got your back," *International Journal of Innovative Studies in Sociology and Humanities (IJISSH)*, vol. 4, no. 3, pp. 18–26, 2019.
- [47] A. L. Duckworth, *Grit: The Power of Passion and Perseverance*. New York: Scribner, 2016.
- [48] D. S. Yeager *et al.*, "Boring but important: A self-transcendent purpose for learning fosters academic self-regulation," *Journal of Personality and Social Psychology*, vol. 107, no. 4, pp. 559–580, 2014, doi: 10.1037/a0037637.
- [49] X. Huang, J. Zhang, and L. Hudson, "Impact of math self-efficacy, math anxiety, and growth mindset on math and science career interest for middle school students: the gender moderating effect," *European Journal of Psychology of Education*, vol. 34, no. 3, pp. 621–640, 2019, doi: 10.1007/s10212-018-0403-z.
- [50] S. C. Noh and A. M. A. Karim, "Design thinking mindset to enhance education 4.0 competitiveness in Malaysia," *International Journal of Evaluation and Research in Education (IJERE)*, vol. 10, no. 2, pp. 494–501, 2021, doi: 10.11591/ijere.v10i2.20988.
- [51] A. Prihatini, "The development of research on learning Indonesian as a second language: A bibliometric analysis," (in Indonesian) *KEMBARA: Jurnal Keilmuan Bahasa, Sastra, dan Pengajarannya*, vol. 9, no. 1, p. 56, 2023, doi: 10.22219/kembara.v9i1.23216.
- [52] A. Campbell, T. Craig, and B. Collier-Reed, "A framework for using learning theories to inform 'growth mindset' activities," *International Journal of Mathematical Education in Science and Technology*, vol. 51, no. 1, pp. 26–43, 2020, doi: 10.1080/0020739X.2018.1562118.
- [53] R. M. D. Mesler, C. M. Corbin, and B. H. Martin, "Teacher mindset is associated with development of students' growth mindset," *Journal of Applied Developmental Psychology*, vol. 76, no. 1, p. 101299, 2021, doi: 10.1016/j.appdev.2021.101299.
- [54] S. K. Patrick and E. Joshi, "'Set in Stone' or 'Willing to Grow'? Teacher sensemaking during a growth mindset initiative," *Teaching and Teacher Education*, vol. 83, no. 1, pp. 156–167, 2019, doi: 10.1016/j.tate.2019.04.009.
- [55] R. Ronkainen, E. Kuusisto, and K. Tirri, "Growth mindset in teaching: A case study of a Finnish elementary school teacher," *International Journal of Learning, Teaching and Educational Research*, vol. 18, no. 8, pp. 141–154, 2019, doi: 10.26803/ijlter.18.8.9.
- [56] F. S. Seaton, "Empowering teachers to implement a growth mindset," *Educational Psychology in Practice*, vol. 34, no. 1, pp. 41–57, 2018, doi: 10.1080/02667363.2017.1382333.
- [57] A. Prihatini and Sugiarti, "The image of the new curriculum: teacher readiness in implementing Merdeka curriculum," (in Indonesian) *GHANCARAN: Jurnal Pendidikan Bahasa dan Sastra Indonesia*, pp. 58–70, 2022, doi: 10.19105/ghancaran.vi.7447.
- [58] A. Prihatini, S. Sugiarti, T. A. B. Ambar Sari, and I. N. Nisa, "Pedagogical competence of high school teachers in implementing multiliteracy learning as a form of independent learning," (in Indonesian) *Edukatif: Jurnal Ilmu Pendidikan*, vol. 4, no. 5, pp. 6823–6831, 2022, doi: 10.31004/edukatif.v4i5.3020.
- [59] A. B. I. Bernardo, "Socioeconomic status moderates the relationship between growth mindset and learning in mathematics and science: Evidence from PISA 2018 Philippine data," *International Journal of School and Educational Psychology*, vol. 9, no. 2, pp. 208–222, 2021, doi: 10.1080/21683603.2020.1832635.
- [60] J. M. Murray, S. Komisarov, S. L. Cook, and B. L. Murray, "Predictors for growth mindset and sense of belonging in college students," *Journal of Pedagogical Sociology and Psychology*, vol. 4, no. 1, pp. 66–85, 2022, doi: 10.33902/jpsp.202213791.
- [61] D. S. Yeager *et al.*, "Teacher mindsets help explain where a growth-mindset intervention does and doesn't work," *Psychological Science*, vol. 33, no. 1, pp. 18–32, 2022, doi: 10.1177/09567976211028984.
- [62] J. Yu, P. Kreijkes, and K. Salmela-Aro, "Students' growth mindset: Relation to teacher beliefs, teaching practices, and school climate," *Learning and Instruction*, vol. 80, no. 4, pp. 1–11, 2022, doi: 10.1016/j.learninstruc.2022.101616.
- [63] T. Nie, Q. Yan, and Y. Chen, "Authoritative parenting style and proactive behaviors: evidence from China?" *Sustainability (Switzerland)*, vol. 14, no. 6, 2022, doi: 10.3390/su14063435.
- [64] H. B. Utomo, V. Iswantiningtyas, and D. Yulianto, "Be strong or weak: the contribution of parenting style toward parent involvement motivation in accompanying children during learning from home," *Journal of Educational, Health and Community Psychology*, vol. 10, no. 4, p. 686, 2021, doi: 10.12928/jehcp.v10i4.22280.

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